

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_type2_d_Topo		
Created on:	4/15/2021 9:44:27 AM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	14.16	µm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.2160	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_t...filtered (As 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\...\Kremasti4_LSM_50x_type2_d_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/15/2021 9:44:27 AM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	2.265	μm	
Min:	-1.547	μm	
Max:	0.7179	μm	
Size:	104849	digits	
Spacing:	0.0216	nm	
NM-points ratio:	3.239 % (291487 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	Kremasti4_LSM_50x_ty...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/15/2021 9:44:27 AM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	2.265	μm	
Size:	104849	digits	
Spacing:	0.0216	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	0.2559	μm	
Ssk	-0.754		
Sku	5.121		
Sp	0.7152	μm	
Sv	1.550	μm	
Sz	2.265	μm	
Sa	0.1952	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	87.98	%	
Smc	0.3092	μm	
Sxp	0.5715	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	21.13	μm	
Str	0.2403		
Std	33.75	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.1278		
Sdr	0.7925	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.009639	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vv	0.3188	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmp	0.009639	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmc	0.2181	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvc	0.2826	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvv	0.03628	μm ³ /μm ²	

Analyses:	
ISO 25178	8.
Furrow	9.
Texture direction	10.
Texture isotropy	11.
SSFA	12.

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	1.542	µm
Mean depth of furrows	0.2743	µm
Mean density of furrows	4481	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	45.00	°
Second direction	89.99	°
Third direction	0.02309	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	74.98	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

